

Impact of Social Activism on their Student Performance: "A Study of Students in Sindh University Campus Naushahro Feroze & Dadu"

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Abstract

this research paper is about social activism and its impacting on student's performance having a study of district Naushahro Feroze and Dadu. Social Activism and Students politics are very issue in academic practices, students have involved nowadays in social issue that has big impact on their academic career. Social Activism is tested through Humanity, Interpersonal Discussion and Academic Issues these items are tested through cronbach alpha which shows better consistency (0.884), also variables are tested with co-relation analysis for measure the strength of relationship among variables and demographic profiles of every participant represent with frequency distributions.

Key Words: Student Performance, Social Activism, Humanity.

Introduction

As the journey of globalization has reached to its escalated degree-which had made this world a global village-it has also taken the socialization along itself which produced a need to make aware ourselves that how much the participation in socialism is necessary or not. The purpose of this research is to counter the results of social participation in the student life that, how a student is managing its time to spend on his study and partly from that on social issues, as well. Educational institutes are contemplating to emphasis on becoming of students more active in the local and global grounds of socialism.¹[Chekering & Stamm, 2002]. The university officials are planning to make sure the participation of students in socialism to meet the new trends and to perform social responsibilities as well. [AACU, 2002]. Higher education is the social tool which is more related to the social justice, in this regard it makes people aware of their role to participate in the societal wellbeing and they usually are the harbingers of the change[Carwile, Lee, and Brant, 2003].

In nutshell, social participation is the significant weapon not only for its stakeholders but also for state and individual as well. Every civilian is not only bound just to participate in it, but it also lies his duty that he should avail his portion of efforts for the society to enhance operations of public institutions and make them constructive, from that he and all stakes of society can trace the benefits in bulk quantity. It purifies the passion of democracy, and it involves individuals in self-determined decision making [Braungart & Braungart, 1991 Zucher, & Ostrove, 1998;].

Usually education has the more influence on all the masses, so that it has the widely relation with the social participation. The purpose of this study is to showcase the impacts and effects of the socialism on the students' performance. As the social participation is on high nod, so that it is very much necessary to counter its impacts on the student's studies. As we know that socialism is highly practiced in the local educational institutes of the country. So, we must find out some its reasons that why students are being participated in the social activities rather than to join their study based activities, and make them completed first and then go to serve the society fully.

Usually, the higher education is a platform where the social circumstances are being observed and the majority of students are participated in it. The higher institutes like universities are creating the opportunity for students to be part of such activity (Merideth L, Weiss). Such kind of activities may consist of campus' internal issues and

probably these issues sometimes representing whole societal issues when they become a point of consideration for all (Lisa O Shuller). Although these institutes are also enhancing the students' rational skills when they become part of these activities such as understanding to the social problems and its solution, striving to do something for the others, leadership skills and good communication skills as well. (Kethrine R, Baryant Willson).

1.2 Statement of purpose

The question arises that, why educated persons are more behold in the social grounds? [Verba Schlozman and Brady, 1995] have given that detail- education is the much needed element for the survival of social career as it makes a person to know ability of speaking, writing, and to figure out the ongoing challenges of the world. With the high qualified education, it becomes a profound interest of socialism, greatest relevance with election, dearest commitment of ethical values of the society. The student's engagement in local dilemmas and their work for it constituting the ability of students to bring the change [Levien & Cureton, 1998]. They said that 73% of the students in 1960s believed that a single man can flourish the spirit of real socio-economic change. The world-oriented activism has met to a high increase as a result amidst 1960s, 28% of the students marked their participation in social activities. Although, in 1970s, the participation cut off at 19%. By the 1990s, same participation had increased 25% [Levin & Cureton, 1998b]. In that era the purpose of their student differs than the today's participation. Their interest and goal of participation has completely changed regarding the time. [Drier, 1998]. Students activism in their colleges and universities has also produced a chance of social change [Bickford & Reynolds, 2002]. Their efforts are not only self-oriented but are for others as well [Colby et al, 2003].

1.3 Research Aim

The aim of study is to present the basic factors which are directly affecting the students study and they too are the barriers in the way of students to acquire their basic life goals by completing their studies first. But unfortunately, this is not so easy to make it finished as it is in saying. For tracing once goals of life, it is very much necessary to have finished the studies first with bolder interest. Perhaps, a student's life is that stage of life which is very keen of enjoying, playing, and participating in joyful activities according to the ongoing situation of the country and their personal interest as well. If the circumstances are in favor of students just only to study, then the scenario will be changed. But, in fact, in our country there are no favoring circumstances to only to study. Like poverty, lack of transparency, violation of human rights, abuses for woman, lack of interest of politicians for wellbeing of education, and corruption, these are the core blockades in the way of study and have charged the youth's interest to work out on it instead of giving full concentration on studies to get these things solved. In nutshell, this case will showcase the entire gap between the activism and studies.

1.4 Research Objectives

- 1) Impacts of student's activism on studies.
- 2) To know its reasons why it is performed.
- 3) Social activism of students at Sindh University Campus Naushahro Feroze is negative to study are positive.

Literature Review

Sindh University is one of the oldest university which recognized soon after the creation of Pakistan. It is the second oldest university of Pakistan which is serving more than 50,000 students and 25,000 students in its campuses across the Sindh. It has 700 faculty members and 25,00 employees. It has seen very uncertain moments in its course of history and has been passed out through many complex and chaotic times. Although in very beginning of 1950s and 60s the university were nothing to do with politics, but it has the issues like

academic, administrative and law and order from its birth. There has been a lot of strikes on academic basis which resulted blockade of academic activities in classrooms and have been also affected the future of middle-class families belonging to the rural Sindh. During the reign of Z.A Bhutto, the University remained off from its academic activities for utmost eight months which none of the university in Pakistan did, because of the students strike to remove current Vice Chancellor(great poet of Sindhi language), Shaikh Ayaz. With respect to time when these kinds of issues became serious than, the goodwill of university got further dents. And cheating and copy culture was observed in its colleges, and boycotts, strikes charged the environment of study at its main campus, Jamshoro. These political circumstances and complexities were met their escalated degree and were not allowed students to focus solely on their studies. Consequently, the goodwill of its brand was dearly damaged in the market, and no one was contemplating to admit their child in Sindh University. Although, these chaotic times also made university to pass through very uncertain steps of its history which no one wants to go, those unfavorable moments also dented the admission of students in bulk. It's very complex to get back its damaged value, and this is what happened to the Sindh University students when they appear, specially, in interviews for jobs or for further studies in renowned institutes, they did not get such response of interviewer which other universities students get (Qurban Khushik). This kind of situation of university lasted more than a decade and its entire stakeholders sustained crucial injuries of educational sense. But, by time, it always kept reviving and never remains same, so as likewise, it evolves for university too, to cheer up loudly and make warmest welcome to the ones who took some efforts to eliminate these multifarious factors which costly damaged the university, and structured several result-oriented rules to run the university in such manners which could benefit its entire mourned stakeholders, and make them once again lively. But the story not being changed fully to consider that, simultaneously, there is no such activities in Sindh university or in its campuses. But still there are many issues of same nature for that, students are making public gatherings and designing some political bodies naming them as Students Welfare Body (SWB), Students Union for Educational Problems (SUEP), Joint Students Federation(JSD) and so on, to pave the way to these problems for solution. It doesn't mean that there should-in universities-not be such activism as it causes study environment but sometimes these are very aggressive to produce such result which can wonders. So that's why, in this thesis we are going to discuss its both aspects, positive as well as negative, to produce result on the basis of surveying it.

2.1 Students Participation.

In nineteenth century most students were coming on the roads to protest against the mourn of their ally in which they were suffering since long time, just like faculty and administrative issues [Braugrant ,1990, Brax, 1981, Horowitz, 1986. The students' issues were not being resolved on the individual vision or same ideology. The students were not keen to alter the society and to gauge the differences of the interest and ideology of their teacher and management and themselves [Brax 1981, DeConde, 1971]. The researchers explained that the period of 1920s, 30s, was the unheeded time for the college and Universities campuses because in this period majority of the students were marked their activism in politics [Kerpelman, 1972, Obear, 1970, Rhoads, 1998]. Although, the students of 1950s were career-based, less interested in politics, and lack involved in the social issues [Braungart, 1990]. In 1960s, the students started their journey to join politics, involve themselves in local and social issues, plebiscite of speech and worked for the civil rights [Braungart, 1990, Ker, 1970]. The increase in the ratio of students acquiring higher studies, it doesn't mean that students will solely attend the college or university but they could also be involved in politics. As in colleges and universities there are number of students' diversities-suppose different casts, region, culture, obviously they need different rights. Therefore, they were constituted different students' bodies in the colleges. In this regard, students were enabled to rise question against the settled doctrines and pursue the purposeful occupation in future [Ker, 1970].

2.1.1 Humanitarianism

The variable humanitarianism is the process of understanding the needs of humans and appreciates them to trace those needs of others. Although it includes the issues just like, right of vote, adequate law and enforcement system, justice, poverty, unemployment, drainage system, labor issues, right of working-labor, human abuses and human violation(Kuh, 1993, p. 24). The practical sense of humanitarianism has the two different aspects which are merely depending upon the students' ability of understanding the needs of others. It has two categories one is high cognitive and other is lower cognitive approaches of understanding the social needs. The students coming in first category they are very dearth to choose means of solving the issues and providing social needs to the needy ones. Society is made up of different people and classes. Some people are the rich and some are the poor. The rich enjoy all their rights such as, right to education, health and property. They also enjoy all the amenities of life. On the other hand, the poor have even no access to the basic rights of the life. Their rights such as education, health and employment are often abused by the rich. They are marginalized in the society. Though, there some people who realize this marginalization very seriously and consequently, they exert to work for those marginalized people to give them their due rights through creation of social bodies. These bodies are sometimes political as well. So, the surge of this humanitarianism catches the attention of university students and resultantly the form some political bodies to engage themselves in the societal works. In Naushahro campus there are some socialists who have created such body which named as Students' Welfare Association (SWA)which aimed at providing the campus students all necessary benefits.

2.1.2One-To-One Discussions

In the universities or its campuses when the political contests are being brought under the discussion than it takes a shape of political activity or political organization. The gist of the designing the political body is to counter the simultaneous issues of the campus. Usually, all the students of university or its campus are not so interested in the resolving the recognized issues of the campus and its students but the political gathering is the only way who makes them aware and compels those uninterested students to work for the resolution of all the recognized problem and to share their portion of efforts for the wellbeing of the students, their education, and their university as well. One-to-One discussions, when students are engaged to share political and social wellbeing thoughts they become preoccupied with the idea to indulge themselves in the political activities and form some political bodies within the university in order to achieve the wellbeing of students and society-members. This proved to be a major factor behind the leading students' social activism activities. In Naushahro Feroze campus, the students often meet at the canteen and share ideas about their study and their other daily routine works. When they come in contact with the one who has no idea about social works or he might not be interested in these work will get little bit clues regarding his own responsibility in the societal wellbeing. Consequently, he will emphasize in the social thoughts. He will think of the people and their needs whether these needs are fulfilled by the government or not. He also realizes his responsibility towards making these needs of people achievable. Slowly and gradually, he will become a social worker. His thinking approach now becomes broader, as with his studies, he also has knowledge of his society- what is going out there- its members, and their needs. This all become due to the discussions among students regarding the society and other routine works. Thus, made it a factor of social activism of the students at Naushahro Feroze campus.

2.1.3Academic Issues

This is, also a crucial factor which is indulging students to become the part of politics. This is the main reason for which students are exerting to get them available in any situation at any cost. The researchers have pointed out that in universities why the politics is being practiced? Because the basic educational rights by which they are being deprived of. Such as issues regarding classes conduction, classes environment, timing, faculty and administrative issues, parking and security problems, incompetent management, late in resolving students' issues, hostile attitude of management towards students and likewise. These are the issues for which students

participating in politics to solve these all with the political official's support when university administrative is not serious to resolve.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Research Methodologies

The ultimate need and gist of this study is to trace the factors which are indulging a student to participate in social and political activities in the universities, and their need of doing so. To know their objective of being doing that makes aware the readers of this study to know the impact of such participation over the student's performance in classrooms. Because, almost, in the universities and its campuses the students' activism is increasing, it doesn't mean only in terms of politics, but it may have observed in various forms only for the sake of well-being of students or societies as well.

3.1 Choice of Research Methods:

The researchers are more often using quantitative approach of the research. Because it is more crucial in generating the desired results of the study for which it is being used. And also is very easy to interpret, evaluate and measure the result. However, the main thing of it is the self-designed questionnaires which may hold true result for the surveyor, and the questionnaire Performa can be filled out without presence of the surveyor (Collis and Hussey, 2009).

3.2 Description of Samples

The sampling purpose in research is to take the selected samples from the entire population rather than bringing up all the data for interpretation (Collis and Hussey, 2009). In this study, the simple random sampling method has been adopted, and have been taken 100 samples from the entire population which are representing the Sindh University Campus Naushahro Feroze students to get the survey done through research questionnaires that how much students were being rushed into the political and social activities and how much they are keen in, during the academic season and what are their comments on that participation.

3.3 Participants

The researcher has selected the 100 samples consisting of the students and teachers which are participated in social activities and those who are supporting this kind of activity in Sindh University Campus Naushahro Feroze. Having the age of 19-50.

3.4 Questionnaire Design

Questionnaires are being structured for the purpose to get opinion of the participants. And are distributed among all the participants and in return, the respondents are giving response to them (Devas, 2002). The total 24 questionnaires are designed on the basis of factors which are the basis for the student's activism in politics. It

has 4 variables on which they are designed, they are, 1) Demographic, 2) Humanity, 3) Interpersonal Discussions, 4) Academic Issues. The first five questions are about the demographic to know the age, department of study, occupation of participants whether they are teacher or student. Second five questions are about Humanity to know that the students who are humanists are performing campaign for students right or not. The forthcoming five questions are about the second variable which is Interpersonal discussions among students which is more often found in universities. The purpose of constituting this variable is to know that how much interpersonal political discussions have influence over the other listener students to make their inclination too to participate in such activities for the welfare of their own and their other colleagues as well. And the last five questions are about the Academic issues to know that how much the academic issues are compelling a student to go to the path of politics to get these issues resolved, this is the core element behind the students' activism in politics. The questionnaires are in easy English language and they followed the Likert type of questionnaires in which tick options are available against various choices, the respondent needs to understand it and has to tick on his preference to any of the provided option.

3.5 Implementation of Research

The data has been collected during the 2-week extent of time from different students of Sindh University Campus Naushahro Feroze. Total 100 questionnaires copies were given to each respective participant to read it out and make it filled. After getting filled questionnaires the researcher is going to interpret its results in SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software 16.0 version and MS-EXCEL 2007.

3.5 Research hypothesis:

H1=There is significant relationship between humanism and student politics

H2= There is significant relationship between Discussion and student politics

H3= There is significant relationship between Academic issues and student politics

Result and Discussions

Researcher put all data in SPSS, conducted reliability test through different tools of the software. This shows how set of items are closely related with one another. Here, researcher checks the validity of all Likert type questions which possess above given factors; eighteen questions possess Likert type scale and data result is (0.684) which is acceptable and shows excellent level of their internal consistency of selected samples. Table is given below.

4.1 Reliability Test among all the Variables:

The researcher put all the data in SPSS software and conducted the reliability test through the Cronbach alpha. It is one of the tools used to measure the integral consistency among all the items. Here, the researcher checks the validity of all the Likert type questions. The result of this test is (0.884) means 88% which is acceptable and shows that there is excellent integral consistency among all the 25 items. The selected sample table for reliability test among all the items is given below:

Fig. 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.884	25

Above table represents the reliability of all the 25 questions which were used to collect data regarding all the three variables that make students to participate in social activism. The result of these 25 items is (0.884) which means 88%, it means there is strong integrity among all the items.

4.2.1 Gender of the respondents:

(Frequency Distribution table of Gender of respondents)

G

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	56	65.9	65.9	65.9
Female	29	34.1	34.1	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

according to the table highest ratio of gender is male. Males responded 65% while females responded 34%.

4.2.2 AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

A

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25	85	100.0	100.0	100.0

This shows that 85% of respondents who responded our questionnaire were of age between 18-25. Because this study was conducted from university campus and all the population was students having almost same age.

4.2.3 Occupation of the respondents:

O

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Student	77	90.6	90.6	90.6
teacher	8	9.4	9.4	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Among respondents 90% were students and 10% were teachers. The data was collected from both the teachers and the students. They responded positively. The ratio of students is high than the teachers.

4.2.4 Department of respondents:

D

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Business Admin	20	23.5	23.5	23.5
Bs English	20	23.5	23.5	47.1
BsCS	20	23.5	23.5	70.6
BS IT	25	29.4	29.4	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

The data was collected from Sindh University Campus N/Froze. In the campus there were four departments. The students which responded were belonging to these four major departments. The students of Business Administration responded 23%. The students of BS English also responded 23%. Computer science students were also 23% and the students of BSc IT also responded with 29% ratio.

4.3 Correlations

		humantrsm	Discussion	Issues	Students_Politics
humantrsm	Pearson Correlation	1	.823**	.748**	.514*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003	.001	.050
	N	85	85	85	85
Discussion	Pearson Correlation	.823**	1	.522**	.441**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003		.000	.000
	N	85	85	85	85
Issues	Pearson Correlation	.748**	.522**	1	.335**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.002
	N	85	85	85	85
Students Politics	Pearson Correlation	.214*	.441**	.335**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	.000	.002	
	N	85	85	85	85

In this study there is three variables so proving them the researcher has applied correlation test. Correlation, basically, is the tool of inferential statistics used to determine the relationship among dependent variable

(students' activism) and independent variables (humanitarianism, political discussions, and academic issues). It determines how these four variables correlate each other. The values of correlation stemming from -1.00 to +1.00. if the value of correlation is 0.01 to 0.25, it means weak but positive correlation. If the value is ranging from 0.25 to 0.50, it shows moderate positive correlation. If the value from 0.50 to 0.75, it shows strong positive correlation. If the value is 1.00 it means that variables are perfectly and positively correlated. If value is zero, it means there is no correlation among variables. On the other hand, if the value is -0.01 to -0.25, it means weak negative correlation. If value is -0.25 to -0.50, it means moderate negative correlation. If value is -0.50 to 0.75, it means strong negative correlation. If value is -1.00, it means there is perfectly negative relationship among variables.

4.4 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The first hypothesis of this study is Humanitarianism. It suggests that how the variable Humanitarianism affects the students to participate in social activities aside from their studies. Hypothesis shows positive relation between humanitarianism and students' activism. It was measured through questionnaire. Both were checked through Pearson's coefficient Co-relation. The value is (0.334). it means there is positive correlation between variable Humanitarianism and students' activism.

The second hypothesis, Students' Discussions, states that it has positive relation with the students' activism. It is measured through research questionnaire. These two variables were checked through Pearson's coefficient Co-relation. The value is (0.823) which means strong positive correlation between Students Discussion and Students' activism.

The third hypothesis, Academic Issues, also shows positive relation with student's activism. These two variables were measured through research questionnaire. Both of the variables then were checked in Pearson's coefficient Co-relation. The value is (0.748) which means there is strong positive correlation between the variable academic issues and students' activism

Conclusion

To sum up all the discussions of this thesis, we will reach a conclusion that this study shows, what is the importance of social activism in the student life, and how the students are indulged in it. This study primarily is focused on University of Sindh's campus Naushahro Feroze, that's why it has given the results about that particular campus that how students of Naushahro campus are engaged in social activism and what are its impacts on the study of the students. Though, in general, there are some factors which force students to become social activist. These factors may include: humanitarianism, one-to-one discussions, and academic issues. Firstly, humanitarianism, it showed that when a person(student) is humanitarian he will consequently rush to social activities to help his people who lack in the basic needs and amenities of the life. Society is made up of different people and classes. Some people are the rich and some are the poor. The rich enjoy all their rights such as, right to education, health and property. They also enjoy all the amenities of life. On the other hand, the poor have even no access to the basic rights of the life. Their rights such as education, health and employment are often abused by the rich. They are marginalized in the society. Though, there some people who realize this marginalization very seriously and consequently, they exert to work for those marginalized people to give them their due rights through creation of social bodies. These bodies are sometimes political as well. So, the surge of this humanitarianism catches the attention of university students and resultantly the form some political bodies to engage themselves in the societal works. In Naushahro campus there are some socialists who have created such body which named as Students' Welfare Association (SWA) which aimed at providing the campus students all necessary benefits. Secondly, the other factor of students' social activism is One-to-One discussions. When students are engaged to share political and social wellbeing thoughts they become preoccupied with idea to

indulge themselves in the political activities and form some political bodies within the university in order to achieve the wellbeing of students and society-members. This proved to be a major factor behind the leading students' social activism activities. In Naushahro Feroze campus the students often meet at the canteen and share ideas about their study and their other daily routine works. When they come in contact with the one who has no idea about social works or he might not be interested in these work will get little bit clues regarding his own responsibility in the societal wellbeing. Consequently, he will emphasize in the social thoughts. He will think of the people and their needs whether these needs are fulfilled by the government or not. He also realizes his responsibility towards making these needs of people achievable. Slowly and gradually he will become a social worker. His thinking approach now becomes broader, as with his studies, he also has knowledge of his society- what is going out there- its members, and their needs. This all become due to the discussions among students regarding the society and other routine works. Thus, made it a factor of social activism of the students at Naushahro Feroze campus. Thirdly, the academic issues of the campus are also made students to become socially and politically active. The researchers have pointed out that in Naushahro campus why the students' activism is being observed? The answer to that question is that the students are being deprived of basic educational rights, such as issues regarding classes conduction, classes environment, timing, faculty and administrative issues, parking and security problems, incompetent management, late in resolving students' issues, hostile attitude of management towards students and so on. These are the issues for which students become socially active. To conclude, the entire study says that students' social activism is being practiced due to some factor, however, if these factors are addressed well by the university campus then, the students will become fully concentrated only to their study. ***“Education is most powerful weapon by which you can change the entire world”***. It means without proper education no one can get its goals of life achieved. So, exerting for societal wellbeing, we must exert for education first. When we become educated then we will be able to make our society more progressive and prosper.

Recommendations for Practice and Future Research

This study suggests several recommendations for student affairs practice and future research.

According to HEC (Higher Education Commission) behavioral approach in academic and ready to all students, students issues are enhance to again consider their importance in the students learning process. Students involvement are enhanced to play a very important role in making/evaluating for extra curricula that gives students with some major instruments that are very compulsory for efficient change agents.

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